

Research Article

Distribution of Endangered Wild Snail Species: A Case Study of Federal College
of Agriculture, Akure

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Abstract

The distribution of snail species was conducted at the Federal College of Agriculture Akure in Ondo State, Nigeria. A GPS (Geographical Positioning System) reader was used to map out four randomly chosen locations. Snail samples were collected using three different sampling techniques: direct search, litter sieving, and deep net. A total of 443 snails were collected, representing 3 families and 7 species. The snails identified were Achatina achatina, Achatina Fulica, Monochoides vicinus, Archachatina maginata, Limicolaria aurora, Limicolaria flammea, and Melanoides tuberculata. The most abundant species were Achatina fulica, with 339 individuals and a relative abundance of 76.59%, followed by Achatina achatina, with 7.22%; Archatina maginata, with 6.09%; and Limicolaria flammea, with 6.7%; Monochoides vicinus, 1.4%; and Limicolaria aurora, 1.13%; Melanoides tuberculata was the least abundant, with 4 individuals and a relative abundance of 1.0%. Except for this species of freshwater snail, Melanoides tuberculata, no other freshwater snails were discovered at the fishing dam area. The findings of this study revealed how the number of snails collected varies depending on location and season. It was discovered that the distribution of snail species collected during the wet season is higher in location A (Fishing Dam Area), with 132 individuals, and lowest in location D (Graze Land Area), with 90 snails, when compared to snails collected during the dry season, which are quite low in all four locations. Anthropogenic activities had a significant impact on the snail species in all four study locations. With the help of this research, a variety of snails that live at the Federal College of Agriculture, in the Akure neighborhood, and nearby

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have been identified. Thus, despite being in the heart of the city, this study discovered that the Community had low diversity of snails. Farmers and students harvest snails for their meat, which is harmful to the snail population. The institution's management should work to preserve the forests and protect them from additional human activities that will likely devastate the ecosystem. The residents of the Federal College of Agriculture, Akure, must be educated on the benefits of snails to the environment and ecosystem, as well as their economic importance.

Keywords: Ecosystem, Species, Diversity, Abundance, Distribution, Anthropogenic.

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Introduction

The class of mollusks, which molluscs include both land- and water-dwelling snails. Despite the data suggesting that slugs lack a protective covering, snails and slugs are nearly related because they are both gastropods (Nwadike *et al.*, 2020). Due to their low morbidity, protracted biological process, and adequate preservation capability of their calcareous shells, molluscs are good indicators of environmental narratives and conditions. Snails live in almost every habitat type and are important to the ecology because they breakdown and use nutrients in both terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems while also providing food for a variety of animals and supporting large populations of algae and other detritus. Land snails are preyed upon by a variety of species in the woodland ecosystem and a variety of organisms, including insects (beetles), amphibians, reptiles, birds, and mammals, feast on snails (Auta *et al.*, 2018). One of the most significant groups of invertebrates in terrestrial environments is represented by land snails. They contribute to the formation of soil and the interaction of metallic elements with the soil in forest ecosystems, and they are intended to serve as helpful indicators of environmental aspects (soil pattern and composition, protection, and benefits to the environment) (Zaidi *et al.*, 2021). Since the majority of species are thought to be consumers of degrading plant materials and microbial decomposers such as fungi and microorganisms, land snails are involved in plant litter disintegration (Idohou *et al.*, 2013).

According to Sandeep *et al.* (2012), snail species are an incredibly important component of the forest ecosystem and have the highest known rate of extinction of any major taxonomic group (Rajashekhar *et al.*, 2012). According to Adegoke *et al.* (2010), the main healthy meal that is high in protein has a good iron-to-protein ratio and is low in fats as snail flesh. In the past, the West African diet has included a

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significant amount of land snails that have been collected from the forest. Snails can be caught in the wild, although they typically die more frequently as they try to adapt to various conditions. Forest resources in the Federal Republic of Nigeria are currently at risk due to widespread forest exploitation, land conversion to agriculture, bushfires, grazing, and exploitation of non-timber derivatives as well as overt and covert effects of the extractive industries (Oke, 2013).

Molluscs have relatively short times between known extinctions in the modern era, and many more species are at risk. Molluscs are easy to experiment with, and their calcareous shells hold up relatively well for a short time before degrading. Many creatures that prey on land snail's use their shells as a source of metal, particularly for biological enclose formation, compaction, and osmoregulation (Javaria *et al.*, 2016). Snails have a relatively good spectrum of reported extinctions and are one of the species most vulnerable to environmental change in the forests. Many believe that habitat degradation, habitat fragmentation, and the conversion of tropical forests into plantations in response to the opportune introduction of exotic species are to blame for the majority of the current rise in global land mollusc extinctions (Rajashekhan and Aravind, 2012). However, because they are primarily small animals seeking out a habitat as herbivores and detritivores, and because they significantly contribute to the nutrient cycle through the breakdown of plant litter in the soil, a significant portion of terrestrial snail diversity goes unnoticed by people (Ogbeide *et al.*, 2018; Aronson *et al.*, 2014; Sha *et al.*, 2015).

Land snails appear to play a key role in the sustainability and functioning of ecosystems since they aid in the provision of food for diverse creatures, the breakdown of materials, and the nourishment of soil metallic element capacity (Nunes and Santos, 2012). This is similar to how snails play a crucial role in the chain of chemical transmission from vegetation or plant litter to carnivores (Nica *et al.*, 2013). Such translocation onto the food chain is a highly important eco-toxicological component result. Numerous scholars have argued that environmental condition elements, soil chemistry components, and plant populations have an impact on the distribution and abundance of terrestrial gastropods, arguing that these factors are important to preventing and protecting the terrestrial ecosystem (Lewis-Najev *et al.*, 2020). The forest floor and consequently the species population in it serve as the sole example of the effects of disruption within the forest.

To provide some level of conservation for species within the community, there is linked continual loss of land snail variety with no alleviation. Anthropogenic activities

such as intensive land use, plantations, and deterioration that reduce the variety and alter the community structure of land snails are the principal threats to the snail fauna at the Federal College of Agriculture in Akure. The main objective of the study is to evaluate the snail species in the study area. The specific objectives are as follows:

- i. To identify the types of snails found in the study area
- ii. To describe the diversity and abundance of terrestrial and aquatic snails.
- iii. To ascertain how the season affects the population of land and water snails in the study area.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

The study was carried out between the latitudes of 5° and 15° north and the longitudes of 7° and 14° east in the woodland region of the Federal College of Agriculture in Akure, Ondo State (Table 1). The predominant wind directions were from the SE. The temperature ranges for dry and wet conditions are 22–29 °C and 20–26 °C, respectively (Abulude *et al.*, 2017). The Guinea Savannah in South West southwestern Nigeria can be seen on the grounds of the Federal College of Agriculture, Akure. Tall trees, native grasses, and legumes dominate the vegetation, while some other plant species are considered weeds by nature. The GPS (Geographical Positioning System), Deep Net, specimen bags, and forceps used in the study were all acquired through the Survey Department of the Federal College of Agriculture Akure, Ondo State.

Table 1: The Geographical Location of the Four Areas

S/N	Location	Geographical Location	Description of the Site
1	A	7°16'10.6N 5°13'27.1E	Fishing Upper Dam
2	B	7°16'13.1N 5°13'33.9E	Livestock Farming Area
3	C	7°16'14.7N 5°13'36.6E	Cultivated Area
4	D	7°16'10N 5°13'12.8E	Graze land Area

Source: (Field Survey, 2021)

Sample Collection

A preliminary survey was performed to identify potential snail-inhabited regions. These territories were divided up, and four locations – A, B, C, and D – were chosen.

Since the distribution of snails is not uniform around the world, these are the regions where they are most likely to thrive. Due to land snails' preference for patchy environments, samples from substrates were collected under leaf litter, boulders, logs, and the exfoliating bark of standing or downed dead trees. The four locations (A, B, C, and D) were chosen at random and surveyed. The collection areas were mapped using a GPS reader. Locations C and D are cultivated areas and grazing areas, whereas Locations A and B are the fishing upper dam area and livestock farm areas. The techniques of our direct search approach, litter sieving method (Tattersfield, 1996), and deep net method were employed for the collection of snail specimens. The compilation of the snail samples was primarily done between 8:00 and 10:00 pm when the snails are at their most active (nocturnal). The locations of the samples were marked on the bags that held them with time stamps and permanent markers. The direct search method entails hand-selecting and analysing every potential Mollusca. To choose the notable snails, a physical picking process lasting 30 minutes was performed using long forceps. Additionally, while wearing hand gloves, snails were manually collected from farmlands, banana and plantain leaves, tree branches, and other plants. The topsoil and debris are collected using the litter sieving technique. The procedure of separating litter-dwelling microspecies from large size snails, which are typically found at low densities, is known as litter sieving (De-Winter and Gittenberger, 1998).

Data Analysis

The estimated number of snails was subjected to Simpson's diversity index analysis to determine the relative abundance and diversity index. The relative abundance (A) index makes it possible to examine a species' distribution in a given area and determine whether it is abundant, rare, or extremely rare (Dajoz, 1985). Zaidi (2021) claims that species can be divided into three distinct groups: common species ($A > 50\%$), uncommon species ($25\% \leq C \leq 50\%$), and very rare species ($C < 25\%$). The following formula was used to determine relative abundance:

$$RA = n_i / N * 100$$

where N is the total number of individuals discovered and n_i is the total number of evaluated species.

With Simpson's diversity index, the species diversity was statistically examined. N in the Simpsons' diversity index $D = \frac{1}{\sum (n/N)^2}$

$$D = \frac{1}{\sum \frac{n(n-1)}{N(N-1)}}$$

N is the total number of each species' members.

N is the total number of members of all species.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows the Geographical readings and location of the sites randomly selected for the study. The study area yielded a total of 443 snail species, with 7 species which are *Achatina achatina*, *Achatina fulica*, *Monochooides vicinus*, *Archachatina marginata*, *Limicolaria aurora*, *Limicolaria flammea*, and *Melanooides tuberculata* were among the numerous kinds of snails discovered, each with a number of 32,339,6,26,5,30,4 respectively, as shown in Table 2. Location A (Fishing Upper Dam Place) was the area with the greatest diversity of snail species, whereas Location C (Cultivated Area) had the fewest snails of all the four locations that were mapped for the survey. The overall number of snails collected over the course of the sampling period similarly followed a similar trend, with the largest and lowest numbers of each snail species being found at Location A (Fishing Upper Dam Area) with 155 and Location C (Cultivated Area) with 83.

Table 2: The Distribution of Snail Species Collected in the Different Sites

S/N	Snail Species	Location A	Location B	Location C	Location D	Total
1	<i>Achatina achatina</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	12	68	4	8	32
2	<i>Archatina fulica</i> (Bowdich, 1822)	107	87	64	81	339
3	<i>Monochoide vicinus</i> (Muller, 1774)	6	0	0	0	6
4	<i>Archatina marginata</i> (Swainson, 1821)	13	6	2	2	27
5	<i>Limicolaria aurora</i> (Jay, 1839)	2	0	1	2	5
6	<i>Limicolaria flammea</i> (Muller, 1774)	11	7	8	4	30
7	<i>Melanooides tuberculata</i> (O..F Muller, 1774)	4	0	0	0	4
	<i>Total</i>	155	108	83	97	443

Source: (Field Survey, 2021)

Table 3: Relative Abundance of Snail Species Present at the Study Area

S/N	SNAIL SPECIES	SNAIL FAMILY	TOTAL	ABUNDANCE%	SPECIES CATEGORIES
1	<i>Achatina achatina</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Achatinidae	32	7.2	Very rare
2	<i>Archatina fulica</i> (Bowdich,1822)	Achatinidae	339	76.59	Common
3	<i>Monochoide vicinus</i> (o.f Muller1774)	Hygramiidae	6	1.6	Very rare
4	<i>Archatina marginata</i> (Swainson 1821)	Achatinidae	27	6.09	Very rare
5	<i>Limicolaria aurora</i> (Jay 1839)	Achatinidae	5	1.13	Very rare
6	<i>Limicolaria flammea</i> (Muller 1774)	Achatinidae	30	6.8	Very rare
7	<i>Melanoides tuberculata</i> (O.F Muller 1774)	Thiaridae	4	1.0	Very rare

Source: (Field Survey, 2021)

Table 3 shows the relative abundance of the species of snails found in the study area. At the four sites, *Melanoides tuberculata* was the least abundant species, with a relative abundance of 1.0 percent, followed by *Archachatina fulica*, with a relative abundance of 76.5 percent. In general, Location A was the only place where *Monochoides vicinus* and *Melanoides tuberculata* were found, whereas Location B did not have *Limicolaria aurora* (Livestocks/Livestock farm area). All of the sampled areas contain *Achatina achatina*, *Achatina fulica*, *Achatina marginata*, and *Limicolaria flammea*. The *Achatinidae* family is represented by 97.87 percent of the species taken from the entire sample region and is the most prevalent and prolific family, followed by

Hygramiidae (1.4 percent) and *Thiaridae* (1.0 percent), which is the least numerous family.

Table 4: Simpson's Index of Species Diversity

S/N	SNAIL SPECIES	SNAIL FAMILY	TOTAL	DIVERSITY	$N(n-1)D = \sum(n/N)^2$
1	<i>Achatina achatina</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Achatinidae	32	992	D=0.59
2	<i>Archatina fulica</i> (Bowdich,1822)	Achatinidae	339	114582	
3	<i>Monochoide vicinus</i> (O.F, Muller1774)	Hygramiidae	6	30	
4	<i>Archatina marginata</i> (Swainson 1821)	Achatinidae	27	702	
5	<i>Limicolaria aurora</i> (Jay 1839)	Achatinidae	5	20	
6	<i>Limicolaria flammea</i> (Muller 1774)	Achatinidae	30	870	
7	<i>Melanoides tuberculata</i> (O.F,Muller 1774)	Thiaridae	4	12	$N\sum n(n-1)$
	<i>Total</i>		442	117208	

Source: (Field Survey, 2021)

Simpson's Index of Species Diversity is depicted in Table 4. The Simpson index of species diversity was 0.59, as seen in the table. It also recommends for more strict conservation measures to stop hunters and students from abusing the available resources, as the result indicates that it had a reasonably high variety.

Table 5: Seasonal Changes in the Number of Snails Gathered

SEASON	Location A	Location B	Location C	Location D
DRY SEASON	23	8	8	7
WET SEASON	132	100	75	90
TOTAL	155	108	83	97

Source: (Field Survey, 2021)

Table 5 shows the seasonal variations in the number of collected snails. This outcome demonstrates how the quantity of snails collected fluctuates depending on the location. The Fishing Upper Dam Area (Location A) had 135 snails gathered, the Livestock Farm Area (Location B) had 108 snails, and the Graze Land Area (Location D) had 97 snails collected. With only 75 snails throughout the wet season, the cultivated area had the lowest snail collection. During the dry season, 23 snails were discovered in the fishing dam area (Location A), and there were 8, 8, and 7 snails in Location B, Location C, and Location D, respectively.

Discussion

The number of species identified during this study is very high compared to other studies conducted in the southeastern and southwestern Nigeria, (Osunsina *et al.*, 2016; Nwadike *et al.*, 2020), although not as much as the data from the Okomu National Park (Oke and Aloban, 2006), the Omo Forest Reserve (Oke, 2013), and the vulnerable and protected forest regions of Ekiti state (Ogbeide *et al.*, 2018). In a related vein, the study region is rich in mollusc species, particularly those belonging to the family *Acharitidea*, which is common in the study area. Every location has a unique diversity of mollusc species. The reproductive pattern and hunters' perception of the species may be to blame for the abundance of *A. fulica* in the four locations. The number of eggs laid and hatched by *A. fulica* during the rainy season, which ranged from 100 to 500, may be related to the increase in the species population in the research area. Due to its size, the *A. fulica* snail was once unwelcome in some areas of southern Nigeria. It also serves as a host to parasitic organisms such as the rat lungworm, *Angiostrongylus cantonesis* (Meyer and Cowie, 2010).

The most common species, *A. fulica*, is prominent because it is resilient, has a wide geographic distribution, and can live in any setting (Albuquerque *et al.*, 2008).

According to species responses to environmental changes, fluctuations in species abundance have been explained, and certain organisms within communities behave incongruently to environmental changes (Gonzalez- megias *et al.*, 2008). According to reports, *A. fulica* is one of the worst snail pests in tropical and climatic zone regions. Despite the fact that their small size limits how much material they can consume per animal, the aggregative nature of the infestations will severely harm infected plants (Raut and Barker, 2002). The most prevalent and well -accepted species of snail in Nigeria is *A. marginata*, however, despite this, there aren't few of them, as farmers and hunters in the research region depend on them for their livelihood.

In Nigeria, *A. marginata* is a prized and important source of protein for people. Human activities have made it less common in some southern Nigerian regions where it was once abundant. The threat to biological diversity includes a variety of factors, including overuse of natural resources, environmental degradation, and pollution (Pullin, 2002). The limited lowland trees are being cleared for agriculture and for wood, which puts the land molluscs of the Federal College of Agriculture Akure under danger. *Melanoides tuberculata*, also known as red-rimmed melania, is the only freshwater species that can be found at site A (Fishing Upper Dam Area), and its population is relatively low there. A medium-sized, primarily freshwater snail found in warm-temperate to subtropical regions, *Melanoides tuberculata* has, also lives in estuaries with marine salinities (Barroso and Matthews-Cascon, 2009). Location C has very little *L. aurora* population (cultivated area).

The study area's cultivated plants may all be eroded by this species, an agricultural pest. Despite this, it is not only detrimental to agriculture but also has some positive aspects. For example, the flesh of the snails can be used as a source of protein in fish feed (Madu *et al.*, 2006). The family *Achatinidae* of land snails includes the genus *Limicolaria*. The snails in this genus are commonly referred to as garden snails. The species of this genus known to exist in the West African subregion include *L. aurora* and *L. flammea*. According to Awodiran and Ogunjobi (2016) , the genus *Limicolaria* and other *Achatinids* are significant crop pests that, when introduced to a new habitat, can disrupt the native ecosystem. Due to the significant decrease in precipitation during this time, and the fact that the majority of snails hibernate or aestivate at this time, there was a loss in the diversity of snails compiled in the dry season compared to the rainy season. It has been determined that humidity and water accessibility are extremely important for snails. Snails prefer a damp, not wet, environment. Although their environment should not be saturated with water, snails crave water (Ejidike

2009; 2013). Food and shelter were definitely found to be significant factors in determining dispersal over habitats. The distribution of snails across habitats at the beginning of the descending season was mostly accounted for by food. Land snail distribution and migration are influenced by a variety of factors, including vegetation, environmental factors, and soil quality (Lewis- Najev *et al.*, 2020).

Conclusion and Recommendation

This study served as the initial inventory of snail species provided to the Federal College of Agriculture in Akure. The purpose of the research was to identify the different types of snails that live in the area as well as their habitats. The snail species are sparsely distributed in the four study locations with only seven species of snails discovered and the commonest species is *Achatina fulica*. This study concluded that the snail variety in the population is low. Farmers and college students who hunt snails for their meat have an adverse effect on the snail population. Therefore, it is advised that anthropogenic activities be curbed because they destroy the environments necessary for snail reproduction and survival. The institution's management should try to protect the forests from further human activity that will probably destroy the ecosystem. The Federal College of Agriculture, Akure populace, must be educated on the benefits of snails to the environment and ecosystem as well as their economic significance.

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